

The Rule of Civics Education Teachers to the Development of Students' Moral Intelligence

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ABSTRACT: This study attempts to define and clarify the role of Civics education teachers in the moral intelligence development of students. This study used a descriptive qualitative method to look at the phenomenon that the research subjects encountered. Data is collected through observation, interviews, and documentation. Nine people made up the study's informants, who were chosen through the purposive sample method. The findings indicated that SMP Negeri Kendari 1 students had developed their moral intelligence through instruction in and reiteration of moral principles, discussion of and demonstration of concrete moral examples indirectly integrated with subjects and group learning processes, and encouragement of participation in extracurricular activities as a means of fostering students' morale, particularly tolerance and self-control. Consequently, it can be said that Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari actively contribute to students' moral intelligence development by incorporating the inculcation of moral intelligence values into the learning process, discussing subject matter and associating it with moral intelligence values, encouraging extracurricular activities, and providing examples or models about people who have moral intelligence values. Civics education teachers play a crucial role in helping students acquire moral intelligence, which is necessary for the development of morally upright citizens who can build civilizations that uphold societal norms and values.

KEYWORDS: Civics Education, Moral Intelligence, Teacher's Role.

INTRODUCTION

In the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teacher and Lecturer, it is stated in article 1 paragraph (1) that teachers are professional educators whose main responsibility is to educate, teach, guide, direct, train, assess, and evaluate students, beginning with formal education and continuing through primary, elementary, and secondary school. Three facets of competence cognitive facets (knowledge), affective facets (attitudes), and psychomotor facets (skills) are the objectives of education as it occurs in schools. All of these variables are interconnected, but the teacher has so far made a mistake by prioritizing the cognitive component over the attitude and psychomotor components when mapping out the achievement of these factors. As a result, there are numerous instances of moral transgressions occurring all around us, and the perpetrators are typically adolescents or even young children, who are still students (Rahman, 2019).

Moral transgressions are a frequent occurrence, which motivates the government to alter the paradigm of education. Every school is required to pay attention to how education is implemented in order to shape students' attitudes. The government's efforts to promote character education since 2009 is one indication of its worry. Character education has experienced numerous issues throughout implementation, making it appear less successful. The material of character education is essentially covered in Civics education, which was formerly known as Moral education, thus this is not a problem for Civics education teachers.

Moral intelligence, as defined by Lennick & Kiel (Rahman, 2019), is the ability to decide how human principles should be applied to values, goals, and personal action. Pranoto (2020) explains that morally superior traits are necessary for children to succeed in life, both at home and at school. Children need moral character, not simply academic prowess, particularly when interacting with others. Children who exhibit high moral standards are referred to as morally intelligent children. Additionally, Pranoto (2020), indicates that moral development in children occurs continuously over the course of their lives. Individual and social factors have an impact on moral intelligence. The relevant personal characteristics include temperament, self-control, self-esteem, age and IQ, education, social interaction, and emotions, whereas the relevant social characteristics include family, peers, schools, the media, and society, the potential to learn better morality by developing children's moral capacity and supporting them with a

supportive environment. A child's moral intelligence rises when he masters one virtue, and he eventually reaches a higher degree of moral intelligence.

Borba (Pranoto, 2020; Rahman, 2019; Kristina, 2019; Rifa, 2017), lists seven characteristics of a morally bright child's virtues that make up their moral intelligence. The characteristics are outlined below: (1) Empathy; children who have empathy tend to be sensitive; show sensitivity to the needs and feelings of others; read other people's nonverbal cues appropriately and react; show understanding of other people's feelings; behave in a caring way when someone is treated unfairly; shows the ability to understand other people's points of view; and can verbally identify other people's feelings; (2) Conscience; children who have a strong sense of conscience are more likely to be honest and trustworthy, to be able to recognize their mistakes in behavior, to be willing to apologize, to admit the consequences of their inappropriate behavior, and to receive few warnings or reprimands from adults, and refraining from blaming others, (3) Self-control; capable of controlling impulses and urges without adult assistance; easy to calm down when frustrated/disappointed/angry; refrain from physical aggression; rarely needs warnings, persuasion, or reprimands to act morally; waits their turn and rarely imposes their opinions or interrupts; (4) Respect; treating oneself with respect, respecting others' privacy, using a respectful tone of speech, not talking about friends or other people behind their backs, (5) Character; children with a strong character of kindness often share, help, and amuse others without expecting anything in return, refuse to be a part of those who intimidate and make fun of others, and always demonstrate kindness and concern for others by setting an example for them through their parents' or teachers' actions. (6) Tolerance; tolerant children tend to be tolerant of other people regardless of differences, and (7) Fairness; children who have a strong sense of fairness: are very happy about the opportunity given to help others, not blaming others by arbitrary, willing to compromise to meet the needs of others, open-minded, sportsmanship in sports matches, resolves problems in a peaceful and fair way, plays by the rules.

Parents of students typically reply affirmatively, indicating that they completely agree, with the teacher's responsibility in establishing values, ethics, morals, and proper education. It is understandable that a set of laws governs how children behave. It might be argued that the teacher has a crucial influence in influencing whether or not student's attitudes on acting as members of society conform to societal norms.

One of the key determinants of the success of any educational endeavor is the teacher, who also serves as an educator and a teacher in schools. Teachers must possess the necessary learning capabilities or abilities in order to raise the standard of teaching. Because of this, the teacher's role always dominates educational innovations, especially those that improve curricula and human resources as a result of educational efforts (Abidin, dkk., 2015). Civics education subject concentrates on how students develop their identities or attitudes. Due to this, the role of a Civics education teacher goes beyond merely imparting knowledge; they also need to offer suitable strategies for helping students develop their moral intelligence in daily life, including in the contexts of the home, the community, and school, in accordance with societal norms and regulations (Handayani & Elan, 2023; Wulandari, dkk., 2021; Winurini, 2016; Notosrijoedono, 2015).

Naturally, student behavior can be well managed when the teacher is in the classroom, but some students' behavior is uncontrollable. For instance, some students frequently chat while the teacher is explaining the lesson material, or they don't pay attention to what the teacher is saying (term is often said by teachers are "going in the left ear out of the right ear"). It is a struggle for a teacher to change the behavior pattern of these students for the better, especially for Civics education teachers, and this is something that not just Civics teachers but also other teachers encounter (Hasyim & Udin, 2021; Hafsa & Afni, 2021).

Teachers, one of the key players in the educational process, must be imaginative while coming up with lessons on Civics. In order to produce students who can grow themselves into decent citizens, teachers must have wide knowledge, excellent teaching techniques, and expand students' personalities. Four primary criteria professional competence, professional effort, appropriate time allocated to professional activities, and appropriate fit between abilities and work are used to determine whether a teacher is qualified. Schools are frequently the scene of adolescent moral failings like fighting, absenteeism, and cheating. Teachers or educators who specialize in moral education must complete this challenging undertaking.

Consequently, the question of whether it is sufficient to simply counsel or lecture about morals in order to alter students' moral behavior is still open for debate. This is because a variety of factors from children's three main environments their home, their school, and their peers' environments have an impact on their moral development. Children encounter challenges when acting morally because they have underdeveloped instincts, beliefs, and moral sensitivity. According to Suherli, et.al., (2019), the

development of a sense of morality or ethical awareness requires education in the form of role models, counseling, and advice, which serve as practical actions to make decisions regarding the benefits and drawbacks of certain behaviors.

According to Mulyono (2016), a good teacher is one who constantly mentors his students in order to become better people in the future. This entails constantly giving students advice or input that they can use. A good teacher may be a parent, a friend, and is always there for their students. You could be a friend who shares tales of the difficulties that students experience. Arieya continues by saying (Ahmadin & Sabia, 2021; Nurainiah, 2022), a good teacher is one who is sincere in their commitment to provide educational services, is creative, and consistently builds learners' skills and strategies so that it contributes to the advancement of the educational field. In order to develop knowledge, a good teacher must be a professional.

Based on this, it is necessary to have the role of the teacher as an educator who offers good examples, knowledge, understanding, and becomes parents of students while students are at school and provides good and organized supervision in order to have a considerate influence on the development of students' moral behavior in the home environment, school, and the surrounding community in order to create student character that is in accordance with the values and norms that apply. As stated by (Fitri & Na'imah, 2020; Septiani & Nasution, 2018; Setiawan, 2013), students must also be shaped to have excellent moral intelligence as part of a good education, which can be accomplished by setting good examples and providing counseling and assistance. As a result, the teacher's involvement is crucial in completing this admirable mission.

Therefore, character is defined as the principles of human conduct that are expressed in one's ideas, attitudes, feelings, words, and deeds and are founded on religious norms, laws, etiquette, culture, and customs. These principles relate to God Almighty, oneself, other humans, the environment, and the nation of one's birth, in order for children to maintain self-control in the face of external factors that might have an impact on their attitudes and conduct.

Research carried out by (Hermawan, dkk., 2021; Pranoto, dkk., 2022), discovered that there has been a significant drop in the moral character among students who fall into the mild group, including a lack of respect on their part for teachers. Teachers frequently say that today's students are difficult to control, rebellious, and like arguing and criticizing in ways that are inconsistent with moral principles. Some even dare to skip classes while they are in attendance. This is what a teacher needs to correct and address, whether they are Civics education teachers or other teachers, by setting a good example, counseling students about the consequences of juvenile delinquency, and giving them the right advice that they can use as a filter to protect themselves from harmful influences..

Based on observations and interviews with Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, it appears that a variety of strategies and approaches are used to enhance students' moral character, such as integrating it with their academic work, providing extracurricular coaching, engaging in habit-forming activities, and setting an example. All aspects of the school are involved in these activities. Teachers of Civics education also take part in it to raise students' moral intelligence (Observation on February 27th-28th 2023).

Civics education has a significant role in developing idealistic students with strong mentalities who can face and solve future challenges. The environment is the main factor impacting the development of moral qualities since students will repeatedly mimic what they observe in the surroundings of the school. Students in the study areas typically display very poor moral character. This is demonstrated by the conduct of students who use impolite speech or language, as well as by the attitudes and actions of students who are still significantly influenced by their surroundings when it comes to interacting with friends and the teacher's advice. The role of Civics education teachers in fostering students' moral intelligence at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari is what the author is interested in researching.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study's descriptive qualitative research, which focuses on fostering students' moral intelligence, strives to accurately define and characterize individual features or symptoms in a social environment. In this study, there were 9 informants, including 4 students, 4 Civics education teachers as well as the principal from SMP Negeri 1 Kendari who were selected using a purposive sampling technique. The information gathered during this study is consistent with the study's intended topic, which is the moral intelligence of students. Interviews, observations, and documentation are the methods used to gather data; the procedures needed to analyze the data are reduction, interpretation, and conclusion-drawing. After being gathered, research data is subsequently examined

for validity in order to produce data that can be supported by science. This is done by employing source triangulation, technical triangulation, member checking, and adequate references.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

There are seven indicators of students moral intelligence based on the research findings. Students will have a high level of moral intelligence if these seven indications are met, and in order to build moral intelligence, it is necessary to develop the seven indicators. In order to better understand how Civics education teachers can help students develop their moral intelligence, this study looks at seven specific moral competencies: (1) Student's empathy; (2) Student's conscience; (3) Student's self-control; (4) Student's respect; (5) Student's character; (6) Student's tolerance; and (7) Student's fairness.

The Role of Civics Education Teachers in Developing Student's Empathy

Empathy, or sensitivity to other people's feelings, is a mindset that demonstrates strong feelings for how other people feel. Students must mature in order to later become morally intelligent individuals who can conduct social relations in society. The following interview findings give a summary of how Civics education teachers help students build empathy.

"An interview with Abdul Hamid, the principal of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, "Civics teachers at this school must play a very large role in developing student empathy because their teaching about Pancasila must of course intersect with empathy." (Interview March 10th 2023).

"An interview with Ahmad Yani, a Civics education teacher of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, "apart from teaching and demonstrating this attitude through concrete examples, what I can do in developing students' empathy is inseparable from my duties as a teacher. I also connect this to what we study in class. (Interview, March 11th 2023) .

"Ahmad Yani continued, "I try to instill an attitude of empathy for my students during the learning process in class, and I give a lot of advice, examples, and relate it to the subject, and if necessary, I report it to the Guidance and Counseling teacher to provide services." (Interview, March 11th 2023) .

"An interview with Asniar Rahman, a student at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, said that: "Civics teachers usually teach us about empathy within the learning process or outside of class. The Civics teacher at our school then constantly offers advice when lecturing so that we don't get envious, saying that if someone is happy, we should be also happy." (Interview, March 11th 2023).

According to research, Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari help students develop their empathy by using examples, offering guidance, and emphasizing its significance. This is accomplished by incorporating the cultivation of empathy into the Civics learning process..

The Role of Civics Teachers in Developing Student's Conscience

Trustworthy and honest conscience is one that has a great level of courage to own its faults, apologize, and pinpoint the mistakes he did. Students must possess a strong conscience in order to navigate life in society. Teachers of Civics education are therefore required to help students form their consciences. The following interview findings give a summary of how civics teachers help students develop their consciences.

"An interview with Abdul Hamid, the principal of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, "A person with a good conscience is an example of someone who has the fortitude to admit their mistakes. Civics educates about that, hence the function of the Civics teacher is highly important, particularly through learning." (Interview, March 10th 2023).

"An interview with Ahmad Yani, a Civics education teacher of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, "Additionally, I help children grow their consciences while they are in class and give specific examples in all of our school activities." (Interview, March 11th 2023).

"Ahmad Yani continued: In Civics learning, there is a lot of discussion about conscience, and as a Civics teacher, of course, you relate this material to the development of students' consciences" (Interview, March 11th 2023).

"An interview with Asniar Rahman, a student at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, said that: It's usually stressed in class to have the courage to accept faults. The teacher advised us to be sincere and offer sincere apologies to others. Then, from what I've

observed so far, civics teachers usually encourage us to be truthful, forgive, don't lie, and so on.” (Interview, March 11th 2023).

According to research findings, Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari instill conscience (honesty, forgiveness, and the prohibition of lying) in the Civics learning process as well as link Civics learning materials to the concept of conscience.

The Role of Civics Teachers in Developing Student's Self-Control

Self-control is the propensity to wait patiently, refrain from interjecting with comments, and quickly regain composure after being frustrated or disappointed. One component of student's emotional intelligence is self-control, which needs to be strengthened so that later students can evolve into responsible adults who can navigate life in society. The results of the following interviews provide a description of the part Civics education teachers play in helping the students develop self-control.

“An interview with Abdul Hamid, the principal of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Civics education teachers may help students develop their self-control intelligence. In particular, I believe that they should provide lots of examples of how to be independent, compassionate, and resilient in the classroom.” (Interview, March 12th 2023).

“An interview with Sarlota Paruluan, a Civics education teacher of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Student self-control can be strengthened through extracurricular activities, such as sports, in addition to integrating them into the learning process. As such, my responsibility in this situation is to encourage students to participate in extracurricular activities.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

“Sarlota Paruluan continued: “I only urge students to participate in this activity since it is obviously always related to the subject matter, and because self-control can also be fostered outside the classroom, for example, through extracurricular activities.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

“An interview with Indri Ayu Prasetya, a student at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, said that: “Our Civics education teachers frequently encourage us to exercise self-control and avoid being easily angered while we are learning. They also emphasized that playing is playing and that you cannot be outraged or irritated while playing.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

According to research findings, Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari encourage self-control in their students by offering them lots of advise and reassuring them while they are learning. Of course, self-control can also be fostered outside of the classroom. So as a way for students to learn self-control, Civics education teachers never stop encouraging them to participate in extracurricular activities.

The Role of Civics Teachers in Developing Student's Respect

Respect is a mindset that entails being courteous, treating people with respect, keeping one's friends private, and treating oneself with respect. A key component of students' emotional intelligence, respect, needs to be nurtured so that later students can mature into decent individuals who can navigate life in society. The following interview findings provide a summary of the part Civics education teachers play in helping students acquire respect.

“An interview with Abdul Hamid, the principal of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Civics teachers stress the need of self-respect in their lessons so that students can respect others despite their differing ideas, respect themselves, and respect others' right to privacy.” (Interview, March 12th 2023).

“An interview with Sarlota Paruluan, a Civics education teacher of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “By providing examples of how to behave properly, respect for friends' privacy, and other subject matter, I can help students create a respect-based mindset that is inextricably linked to classroom learning activities.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

“Sarlota Paruluan continued: “As a Civics education teacher, it naturally ties up with in-class learning activities by assigning group projects that can help students grow.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

“An interview with Indri Ayu Prasetya, a student at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, said that: “the Civics education teacher often told us in class to be respectful of others before ourselves when we bothered classmates or created noise. We are also often reminded to respect others and not to take our friends for granted.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

Based on research, Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari advise students frequently throughout the learning process in order to instill an attitude of respect for students. Additionally, Civics education teachers always use the group work learning method as a vehicle for instilling an attitude of respect such as respecting the privacy of others, respecting one's own abilities, and be polite to friends during learning.

The Role of Civics Teachers in Developing Student's Character

Characters are an attitude that includes sharing, helping, and entertaining others without expecting anything in return, refusing to be a part of those who intimidate and make fun of others, and always demonstrating kindness and concern for others by following the example of parents and teachers. That also includes saying kind comments that are able to build enthusiasm in others without persuasion. Students' emotional intelligence includes aspects like good character, which must be fostered if they are to grow up to be moral members of society. The following interview findings provide a summary of the part Civics education teachers play in fostering character.

“An interview with Abdul Hamid, the principal of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Civics is connected with character, which is why some people have the adage that if a student's morals are being harmed, ask the Civics teacher; they will be able to identify the issue. Teachers of civics certainly present instances of kindness, animal affection, instead of frightening others, assisting one another, sharing, and entertaining others.” (Interview, March 12th 2023).

“An interview with Sarlota Paruluan, a Civics education teacher of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Naturally, as a teacher, of course I try to develop students' character during the learning process, but it doesn't stop there, I constantly encourage students to be active in extracurricular activities as a medium for developing character.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

“Sarlota Paruluan continued: “Characters can be developed throughout the educational process by instructing or providing real-world examples; they can also be created outside of the classroom, which undoubtedly involves a large number of people.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

“An interview with Hendra Ardiansyah Putra, a student at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, said that: “Of course, our Civics teachers teach us valuable lessons, and always encourage us to tell the truth and avoid deceiving others. They assert that having virtuous character is just as important for success as being honest.” (Interview, March 13th 2023).

According to the research findings, the Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari cannot be separated from their responsibilities as a Civics teacher in order to develop students' character; in other words, they not only teach students about manners but also educate them about manners so that they are more gentle in speaking, in order to increase their love for fellow human beings and refrain from using intimidation. Additionally, Civics education teachers constantly push their students to participate in extracurricular activities that take place both within and outside of the classroom.

The Role of Civics Teachers in Developing Student's Tolerance

Tolerance is a mindset that seeks to eliminate disparities within a group, is approachable and kind, and consistently puts the best interests of others first. In order for students to later be tolerant in society, it is important to cultivate their emotional intelligence in this area as well. The following interview findings give a description of the part Civics education teachers play in encouraging students to be tolerant.

“An interview with Abdul Hamid, the principal of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Along with teaching students about tolerance, the Civics education teacher's job in fostering tolerance in students includes providing instances throughout the course of class. I discovered that Civics teachers encouraged students to support one another by reaching out to fellow students who were having trouble completing their homework when I was observing classes.” (Interview, March 12th 2023).

“An interview with Rasni, a Civics education teacher of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Tolerance must be ingrained in students from a young age, and I certainly teach a lot of notions about tolerance as a Civics education teacher. In addition, I provide students the chance to show tolerance for their friends through the design of my learning activities.” (Interview, March 14th 2023).

“Rasni continued: “As a Civics teacher, it is not challenging for me to help students develop this attitude during the learning process because tolerance is discussed in the course content. In fact, I usually advise them to be open to participating in group activities because there are many that demonstrate how students can grow more tolerant. I'll continue to have a tolerant mindset as a Civics teacher so that I can set a good example for my students.” (Interview, March 14th 2023).

“An interview with Hendra Ardiansyah Putra, a student at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, said that: “Since Pancasila promotes tolerance, we are frequently reminded to always act with tolerance. We are even advised to engage in various activities to help us develop this quality. Then I realized that our Civics teacher must have a lot of tolerance because she often praised our participation in extracurricular activities and informed us that those activities had helped us develop a spirit of tolerance.” (Interview, March 14th 2023).

Based on the research findings, Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari always relate the subject matter to the formation of this attitude in their students. Additionally, tolerance is imprinted in students' learning when they complete tasks, and Civics education teachers usually emphasize the need of participating in extracurricular activities as a forum for fostering tolerance.

The Role of Civics Teachers in Developing Student's Fairness

Fairness is characterized by being extremely grateful for the chance to assist others, not blaming others arbitrarily, being open-minded, willing to make concessions to accommodate others' needs, exhibiting sportsmanship during sporting events, resolving conflicts in a peaceful and fair manner, and abiding by the rules. Fairness is also characterized by being ready to acknowledge the rights of others, which can ensure that they deserve to be treated equally and fairly. The ability to be fair is one part of emotional intelligence that needs to be fostered in order for future students to act as fairly as possible in society. The results of the following interviews provide a description of the part Civics education teachers play in helping students develop a fair mindset.

“An interview with Abdul Hamid, the principal of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “Fairness is also part of student morale and Civics education teachers also play a role in developing this attitude. Many activities carried out by Civics teachers in learning, one of which is carried out by giving a fair value, is enough to teach about fairness” (Interview, March 11th 2023).

“An interview with Sitti Nurjanah, a Civics education teacher of SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, “In order to prevent internal unrest, it is imperative that students have a fair attitude. As a Civics teacher, I regularly encourage my students to treat others fairly and also set an example by grading learning objectives in accordance with their rights.” (Interview, March 14th 2023).

“Sitti Nurjanah continued: “My job as a Civics teacher is to help students acquire a fair mentality by offering them specific examples, such issuing fair grades and sanctions, among other things.” (Interview, March 14th 2023).

“An interview with Melisa Putri, a student at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari, said that: “Even if I'm offended, Civics teachers have set a positive example by awarding grades equitably. If she mentions justice in regular class, look at the television to see people protesting for justice.” (Interview, March 14th 2023).

According to research findings, teachers of Civics education at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari demonstrate a fair attitude by constantly following the standards of honest and fair evaluation and using them when assigning grades to students' learning outcomes.

It also can be inferred from the description above that Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari actively contribute to students' development of moral intelligence by incorporating the inculcation of moral intelligence values into the learning process, discussing subject matter and associating it with moral intelligence values, encouraging participation in extracurricular activities, and providing examples or models of people who have moral intelligence.

Discussion

Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari create moral ideals based on the findings of the research in an effort to raise their students' moral intelligence. This is accomplished by taking an active part, as shown by activities like incorporating the development of moral intelligence values into the learning process, connecting Civics subject matter to moral intelligence values, encouraging extracurricular activity participation as a means of fostering students' moral intelligence values, and making an effort to set a good example as a teacher with moral values.

The seven components of student's moral intelligence can be developed through many of the learning activities employed by students. When students are organized into small, heterogeneous groups for group learning, each group is given a task to perform and is accountable for the assignment in line with the work procedure that has been provided. The teacher indirectly instills moral intelligence values during group work, such as tolerance, where students who are less able to help from students with more abilities, and self-control, where students are given the chance to ask each other questions, and mutual response, as well as an attitude of being able to identify others' strengths and flaws, which the teacher indirectly reinforced. The teacher can assist, inspire, and direct students during this learning to help them develop these moral values.

The study's findings indicate that discussing Civics education material is linked to the growth of certain moral intelligence traits. In this case, the teacher actively contributes to the development of students' moral intelligence by incorporating concrete examples of moral principles into Civics curriculum materials. Every time the learning process is conducted, the discussion of civics subject matter is inextricably linked to the values of discussing students' moral intelligence, allowing the teacher to indirectly

contribute to the development of moral intelligence values because, as a result of this integration, the level of students' understanding of moral values will rise automatically.

The development of moral intelligence can occur both in the classroom during the learning process and outside of it through extracurricular activities. In this case, Civics education teachers have the responsibility of enticing their students to participate in extracurricular activities, both those organized by the school itself and those organized by other organizations outside the school. There are many advantages to be gained from extracurricular activities, especially from social aspects like how students can develop a tolerance value in themselves so that they can show respect for their seniors and others from different backgrounds. Extracurricular activities can also bring friends together for the same activity. Furthermore, extracurricular activities offer a place for students to practice self-control since they foster the practice of waiting their time and learning to refrain from various verbal and nonverbal forms of aggressiveness.

The results of the study also revealed that Civics education teachers actively contribute to students' moral intelligence development by serving as role models or examples of educators with high moral intelligence. Civics education teachers uphold their empathic qualities by consistently prioritizing their responses to both good and bad news, such as by regularly asking students to pray for sick classmates or by addressing any adverse symptoms that may occur from students while they are learning. The Civics teacher exhibits fairness in addition to empathy, particularly when awarding grades for each daily test and emphatically stating that the grades have been issued fairly, in accordance with each student's skills, and with supporting documentation such as students' answer sheets.

Being a role model or an example of a teacher with high moral intelligence is absolutely necessary to achieve the goal of developing students' moral intelligence, given that providing examples or role models especially consistent and ongoing examples from the teacher is far more effective than simply coaching in developing moral aspects.

CONCLUSION

In line with the study findings, moral intelligence is being developed in students at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari. This is accomplished through advising and reminding students about moral principles, talking about and providing concrete examples of moral principles indirectly integrated with subjects and group learning processes, and encouraging students to participate in extracurricular activities as a forum for fostering student morale, particularly tolerance and self-control. As a result, it can be argued that Civics education teachers at SMP Negeri 1 Kendari actively contribute to their students' development of moral intelligence by incorporating the inculcation of moral intelligence values into the learning process, talking about the material and connecting it to moral intelligence values, encouraging extracurricular activities, and setting an example. or depictions of individuals who exhibit moral intelligence.

Based on the findings and recommendations of the study, it is suggested that teachers of other subjects as well as those who specialize in Civics education work to develop students' moral intelligence in order to achieve educational goals in the apprehensive aspect, particularly producing citizens with high moral character who uphold societal values and norms. By participating in providing advice and guidance and monitoring each student's behavior so that they are consistently disciplined and compliant with the rules of applicable school regulations, the security staff at the school must also help the teacher succeed the behavior and attitudes of students in developing the moral intelligence of students.

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Cite this Article: Hamuni, Muhammad Idrus, Aswati, Karsadi, Wa Ode Hijrah (2024). The Rule of Civics Education Teachers to the Development of Students' Moral Intelligence. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 7(5), 2809-2817